

Quantum Algorithm Card for Grover Search Algorithm

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1 Introduction

This document contains an example of a quantum algorithm card for the Grover's algorithm. The card is intended as supplemental material for our paper "Quantum Algorithm Cards: Streamlining the development of hybrid classical-quantum applications", submitted at Second Workshop on Engineering Processes and Practices for Quantum Software (PPQS' 23)¹.

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¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/ppqs23/committee?authuser=0>

Quantum Algorithm Card for Grover Search Algorithm	
Element	Description
Overview	The Grover Search Algorithm was proposed by Grover in 1996. It performs an unstructured search on an unsorted database. The Grover Search Algorithm provides a quadratic speedup compared to classical algorithms. It can find a marked item in an unsorted database of N items using $\sqrt{N}$ queries.
Intended use	The Grover Search Algorithm can be used in situations where there is a need to search through unsorted data to find a specific item that satisfies a particular criterion. It has applications in cryptography, database searching, optimization problems, and more. The Grover Search Algorithm is designed for quantum computers and exploits quantum parallelism to accelerate the search process.
Usage details	To use the Grover Search Algorithm, we need access to a quantum computer capable of executing quantum gates and operations. The Grover Search Algorithm involves the following steps: Initialization: Prepare a superposition of all the possible states. Query Oracle: Apply an Oracle operation that marks the solution(s) we are searching for. Amplitude Amplification: Apply a series of Grover operators to amplify the amplitude of the marked states and reduce the amplitude of the unmarked states as much as possible. Measurement: Measure the quantum state, collapsing it to one of the marked states with a high probability.
Performance metrics	The performance of the Grover Search Algorithm can be evaluated based on its speedup compared to the classical search algorithms.
Limitations	The Grover Search Algorithm is not applicable to all types of searches. It is designed for unstructured search tasks on quantum computers. The Grover Search Algorithm's performance is influenced by the accuracy of quantum gates and quantum hardware. Noise and errors in quantum hardware can negatively impact its performance. Quantum Hardware Requirements: The Grover Search Algorithm requires access to a quantum computer that can execute the necessary quantum gates and operations.
References	Grover, L. K. (1996, July). A fast quantum mechanical algorithm for database search. In Proceedings of the twenty-eighth annual ACM symposium on Theory of computing (pp. 212-219).
Caveats	Constructing the Oracle: The performance of the algorithm heavily relies on constructing an efficient oracle that can mark the solution(s) in the database. Designing a good oracle for complex problems can be challenging. Limited Speedup: While the Grover Search Algorithm provides a quadratic speedup over the classical search algorithms, it does not offer exponential speedup like some other well-known quantum algorithms (e.g., Shor's algorithm for prime factorization), but it has many applications.